

Dominant Flow Driving Mechanics at Different Temporal Scales along the Gulf of Aqaba

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ABSTRACT

Gulf of Aqaba (GA) becomes one of the world most attractive spots nowadays with the massive potential development of Neom City. Thus, it is important to understand the dynamics governing such water volume motion that should have a direct influence on the sustainability of some of the proposed coastal mega-projects such as; The Line, The Cube, Sindalah Island, etc. during severe storm events. The gulf is a unique water body that exists in the Eastern flank at the northern end of the Red Sea (RS) basin. Such uniqueness can be observed in three main features; the semi-confined water body; the elongated shape; and spatially variable bathymetric formation and shoreline irregularity. The domain can be divided into three sub-basins based on the width and depth irregularity; the northern; central; and southern basins. Basically, such wide variation between sub-basins configurations governs the regional horizontal flow circulations of the GA presented with consecutive pairs of flow cells. However, the vertical flow circulation is mostly governed by coastal (i.e., winds) and oceanographic (i.e., density currents and tidal currents) driving mechanisms. The GA basin is too large to be considered as a sea and too deep as well to be considered as an ocean. We believe a fatal mistake is to assume flow velocity consistency along depth as well as studying the GA circulations from a single perspective.

The region is described with high temperatures during the summer. As a result, the upper layer is heated than the lower layer leading to a remarkable stratification of the water volume during that season [1-3]. Moreover, due to combined effect of high evaporation rates [4] and minimal fresh water runoff, GA becomes high-dense seawater in comparison to RS water density [5]. Accordingly, high exchange of water volumes induced by density currents between the GA and RS basins [6]. Once the RS thermos driven inflow penetrates the GA system flowing towards the north tip, the surface flow cools and thus sinks in the lower layer flow at the edges. Attributed current to the thermocline flow is reported in a range of 2-4 cm/s [7].

The wind-driven current plays an important role in GA upper circulation patterns. Most of the time winds are always blowing, by a speed that reaches 12 m/s, along the Gulf stream

pointing from north to south [8]. During the day, the wind is calm at night and increases in speed at morning, reaching its peak in the afternoon as the temperature is maximum. Tidal currents induced in RS are amplifying with additional in and out flows to the GA circulation towards north that is again controlled by the Straits of Tiran (ST) bathymetric configurations [9]. The diurnal tidal constituents are the luni-solar diurnal component (K1) but in regard to the main semi-diurnal constituent is the lunar component (M2) [10]. Tidal flux over the month period occupies the upper surface layer with a depth of 150 m in summer [11].

The three-dimensional (3D) Reynolds-averaged Navier-Stokes' equation, coupled Hydrodynamic-Aquatic Ecosystem Model (AEM3D) developed at the University of Western Australia, was applied in this study. AEM3D is a hydrostatic finite-difference hydrodynamic model that predicts the velocity and temperature distribution on a vertical level grid subject to external environmental forcing. The model employs a three-stage numerical algorithm for scalar transport (e.g., temperature, salinity, or tracer): (1) vertical mixing by the mixed layer model; (2) advection of the scalar field by the resolved flow; (3) horizontal turbulent diffusion using a constant eddy viscosity turbulence parametrization. The fundamental numerical scheme was adapted from the Tidal, Residual, Intertidal Mudflat (TRIM) model [12].

The seabed formation of the GA is unique; therefore, information of bathymetry features was collected from various sources seeking the best resolution as well as accurate description of the gulf basin bottom. These sources are the European Marine Observation and Data Network (EMODnet), Navionics Sonar Maps, Satellite Driven Bathymetry (SDB) and Shuttle Radar Topography Mission (SRTM). Hence, the ground elevations were compiled in order to generate an informative map for the GA. To account for exchange between RS and GA, the grid was forced with an open boundary at Strait of Tiran, where hourly water level data, extracted from ERA5, and previous field observations, presented in Karati et al. [13], of temperature and salinity profiles along 200 m isobath were specified. Surface meteorological forcing was collected from ERA5, in which hourly wind speed, wind direction, relative humidity, air temperature, atmospheric pressure and solar radiation were applied uniformly over the model grid. In addition, initial condition water temperature and salinity profiles data were identified at three locations for each along GA.

A uniform low-resolution grid of 600 m \times 600 m was created to model the hydrodynamics of GA. Although, in the vertical, 75 levels were specified with non-uniform resolution, starting with 1 m at the surface and increasing gradually beneath the depth of the summer thermocline to 40 m spacing at the maximum depth of 1000 m, at which the bed level at deeper zones was set to 1000m. For all simulations, the model ran for 14 days, starting 18 August 2016 and ending 31 August 2016, based on the availability of boundary condition forcing data. The time step was 60 seconds to satisfy the Courant-Friedrichs-Lewy stability condition.

In order to examine the impact of the density currents on the flow circulation of the water column, two hydrodynamic forcing conditions; Scenario 1 of tide fluctuations only and Scenario 2 of tide fluctuation associated with density profiles were tested. In Figure 1, average flow velocities are calculated over the first 200m water depth which is roughly the width of the upper stratified layer at four selected locations along the GA basin longitudinal axis. The plot indicates a significant increase in cumulative velocities around 12 cm/s instead of a negligible velocity induced by a stand-alone tide. Therefore, this is clear evidence on

the significance of considering the density currents vertical profiles in the GA flow circulation bearing in mind that both currents are propagating towards north.

Figure 1. Extracted model average flow velocity over 200m depth at different locations along the basin of tidal only and tidal/density currents at selected random time. Note station 0.0 is at the basin northern tip location.

Furthermore, at a random selected time, as a sample, a velocity participation percentage of each current component is indicated as shown in Figure 2. The plot implies a noticeable contribution of density currents when compared to wind induced currents. The density current can reach out to 80% contribution at one location but not less than 40% anywhere else. Bearing in mind that the two currents are generally opposing in direction while wind currents are only limited to the first few meters of the water column but density currents can extend at least 150 m in depth, the resultant surface wind flow speed can be reduced considerably due to density currents travelling in the against direction attenuating the total current velocity.

Figure 2. Extracted model total average velocity participation percentage over 200m depth at different locations along the basin of three current components at selected random time. Note station 0.0 is at the basin northern tip location.

In conclusion, the performed simulations indicate a remarkable impact of thermodynamics that have to be considered in the flow circulation modelling. This could have a direct influence and implications such as; dissipative turbulence and eddies, internal waves, stagnant/standing flows, and many other environmental negative impacts. Considering these impacts could improve an early warning system for the new coastline. It can be achieved by

implementing an appropriate simulation for water dynamics to identify stagnant locations which may result in environmental risks. For instance, the coast guard can develop contingency plans in order to manage oil spill hazard that may occur within the defined stagnation points.

On the other hand, further hydrodynamics investigation required for the offshore developments within GA shall include, in first place, the flow induced by density currents since it contributes with an average of 53% of total participated currents along GA, as illustrated in Figure 2.

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